

Zorn's Lemma

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In the text *Zorn's Lemma*

https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cluster=13609030796755773403&hl=en&as_sdt=0,5

Daniel R. Grayson summarizes Kneser's proof of Zorn's Lemma given in

Hellmuth Kneser. Eine direkte Ableitung des Zornschen Lemmas aus dem Auswahlaxiom. *Math. Z.*, 53:110–113, 1950. <http://gdz.sub.uni-goettingen.de/dms/load/img/?PID=GDZPPN00238180X>

The purpose of this text is to add more details to Grayson's text. Thank you to Murray Eisenberg for having pointed out Grayson's text to me!

Theorem 1 (Zorn's Lemma). *Let P be a poset all of whose well-ordered subsets have an upper bound. Then P has a maximal element.*

If p is a member of a poset P , we denote by $P_{<p}$ the set of those elements of P which are less than p . We say that a subset D of a poset P is **downward closed** if $P \ni p < d \in D$ implies $p \in D$, that is, if

$$P_{<d} = D_{<d} \tag{1}$$

for all $d \in D$. We define that partial order \preceq on the set of all subsets of P by decreeing that $S \preceq T$ if S is downward closed in T .

Proposition 2. *If D is a proper downward closed subset of a well-ordered set W , and if $m = \min(W \setminus D)$, then $D = W_{<m}$. \square^2*

Proposition 3. *A union of downward closed subsets is downward closed. \square*

Proposition 4. *If \mathcal{W} is a set of well-ordered subsets of P , and if \mathcal{W} is totally ordered by \preceq , then the union $U = \bigcup_{W \in \mathcal{W}} W$ is well-ordered.*

Lemma 5. *In the setting of Proposition 4 each $W \in \mathcal{W}$ is downward closed in U .*

Lemma 6. *If A and D are subsets of a poset P , and if D is downward closed in P , then $A \cap D$ is downward closed in A . \square*

To prove Theorem 1 we assume that P has no maximal element and we try to get a contradiction.

For any well-ordered subset W of P there is an element $p(W)$ in $P_{>W}$, that is, an element $p(W)$ in P such that $p(W) > w$ for all w in W . Indeed, W has an upper bound b , and, b being not maximal, there is a $p(W)$ such that $p(W) > b$.

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²The symbol \square at the end of a statement means that the proof is left to the reader as an easy exercise.

Let \mathcal{W} be the set of those well-ordered subsets W of P such that

$$p(W_{<w}) = w$$

for all w in W . If W is in \mathcal{W} , then, clearly, so is $W \cup \{p(W)\}$. Thus \mathcal{W} (ordered by inclusion) has no maximal element. We will reach the contradiction we are after by showing that \mathcal{W} does have a maximal element, namely the set $U := \bigcup_{W \in \mathcal{W}} W$. Hence, Theorem 1 will follow from

Proposition 7. *The set U is in \mathcal{W} .*

Lemma 8. *A downward closed subset of a member of \mathcal{W} is in \mathcal{W} . \square*

Lemma 9. *If $W, X \in \mathcal{W}$ and $W \prec X$, then we have $p(W) = \min(X \setminus W)$ and $W = X_{<p(W)}$.*

Lemma 10. *The set \mathcal{W} satisfies the assumptions of Proposition 4.*

We now prove the seven remaining statements.

Proof of Lemma 5. Let $U \ni u < w \in W \in \mathcal{W}$, and let us show $u \in W$. We have $u \in X \in \mathcal{W}$ for some X , and we get $u \in W$ because $W \preceq W \cup X$. \square

Proof of Proposition 4. Let A be a nonempty subset of U . There is a W in \mathcal{W} such that $W \cap A \neq \emptyset$, and Lemmas 5 and 6 imply $\min(W \cap A) = \min(A)$. \square

Proof of Lemma 8. Follows from (1). \square

Proof of Lemma 9. Follows from Proposition 2. \square

Proof of Lemma 10. Let $W, X \in \mathcal{W}$. It suffices to show that we have $W \preceq X$ or $X \preceq W$. Assume by contradiction that W and X are incomparable. Let \mathcal{D}_W be the set of all downward closed subsets of W , and define \mathcal{D}_X similarly. By Lemma 8 the sets \mathcal{D}_W and \mathcal{D}_X are contained in \mathcal{W} . Put $D := \bigcup_{E \in \mathcal{D}_W \cap \mathcal{D}_X} E$. Then Proposition 3 implies $D \in \mathcal{D}_W \cap \mathcal{D}_X$. We also have $D \prec W$ and $D \prec X$. Set $w := \min(W \setminus D)$ and $x := \min(X \setminus D)$. Lemma 9 yields $w = p(D) = x$, and $D \cup \{p(D)\} \in \mathcal{D}_W \cap \mathcal{D}_X$, contradiction. \square

Proof of Proposition 7. Lemma 10 and Proposition 4 imply that U is well-ordered. It only remains to show $p(U_{<u}) = u$ for $u \in U$. Since $p(W_{<u}) = u$, it suffices to prove $W_{<u} = U_{<u}$. In view of (1) this follows from Lemmas 10 and 5. \square

Proof of Theorem 1. As already mentioned, the theorem follows from Proposition 7. \square